

**Age and Recent Historical Time Trends in Young People's Environmental Attitudes:
An Individual Participant Data Meta-Analysis**

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Abstract

Today's youth typically feel concerned about climate change. At the same time, some evidence has suggested an "adolescent dip" in environmental attitudes (i.e., beliefs, affect, and/or behavior regarding the natural environment). We meta-analyzed individual participant data of 62,204 young people ($M_{\text{age}} = 14.27$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 3.46$, 49.6% female) from 73 international datasets to provide the most comprehensive estimate to date of how environmental attitudes vary across age from childhood until emerging adulthood (i.e., 8 to 25 years), and across recent historical time (i.e., 2005 to 2024). First, we found no evidence of an overall adolescent dip in environmental attitudes. Rather, we found that age trends depend on how environmental attitudes are conceptualized and assessed. Specifically, endorsement of the new ecological paradigm (i.e., NEP scale) showed small age-related increases that levelled off by late adolescence. Conversely, endorsement of nature utilization (i.e., 2-MEV utilization subscale), reflecting less favorable environmental attitudes, also increased with age. Finally, we did observe an adolescent dip in endorsement of nature preservation (i.e., 2-MEV preservation subscale), as well as in overall and environmental sustainability consciousness (i.e., SCQ). Second, we found no evidence for recent historical time trends. Third, we found exploratory evidence that age trends in environmental attitudes are not universal but depend on gender and world region. We conclude that young people's environmental attitudes have remained largely stable over the past two decades, and that age trends in environmental attitudes are contingent upon their conceptualization, as well as individual and contextual characteristics.

Keywords: environmental attitudes, sustainability consciousness, adolescent dip, age trends

Age and Recent Historical Time Trends in Young People’s Environmental Attitudes: An Individual Participant Data Meta-Analysis

At the current rate of global warming, extreme climate-related events such as heat waves, heavy storms, or torrential rains, are expected to become increasingly common and consequential in the lives of today’s young generations (Thiery et al., 2021). Not surprisingly, young people tend to feel concerned and anxious about climate change and its associated ecological crisis, often more so than adults (Poortinga et al., 2023; United Nations Development Programme, 2021; Whitmarsh et al., 2022). At the same time, there is also evidence to suggest that adolescents hold less favorable attitudes toward the natural environment than both (younger) children and adults (e.g., Baierl et al., 2022; Olsson & Gericke, 2016). In the present meta-analysis, we (a) test the robustness of this so-called “adolescent dip” in environmental attitudes across samples and conceptualizations, and (b) chart recent historical time trends in young people’s environmental attitudes. We aggregated individual participant data from 73 datasets collected between 2005 and 2024 (aggregated sample = 62,204 participants) to provide a pooled estimate of age trends in environmental attitudes from childhood until emerging adulthood (i.e., up to age 25).

Conceptualizing Environmental Attitudes

Environmental attitudes concern diverse aspects of how people relate to the natural environment (e.g., nature appreciation, biodiversity, and pollution), and have been conceptualized in diverse ways (Cruz & Manata, 2020; Hawcroft & Milfont, 2010). One approach conceptualizes environmental attitudes as a set of beliefs that constitute a more or less ecological worldview (e.g., “Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist”; Dunlap et al., 2000). Ecological worldviews are rooted in the fundamental belief that nature has inherent value of its own (i.e., ecocentrism) rather than that it exists primarily for human use (i.e., anthropocentrism). Another approach conceptualizes environmental attitudes as a

constellation of related beliefs (e.g., “Humankind will die out if we don’t live in tune with nature”) as well as affective (e.g., “Dirty industrial smoke from chimneys makes me angry”) and behavioral (e.g., “I always switch the light off when I don’t need it”) tendencies (Bogner & Wiseman, 2006; Breckler, 1985; Kaiser et al., 2010; Schultz, 2001). A third approach conceptualizes environmental attitudes as one component of the broader concept of sustainability consciousness. This concept, tied to UNESCO’s education for sustainable development framework (UNESCO, 2006, 2015), encompasses adolescents’ knowingness (i.e., understanding), attitudes, and behaviors concerning environmental sustainability, as well as social and economic sustainability more generally (e.g., “I think that we need stricter laws and regulations to protect the environment”; Gericke et al., 2019; Kopnina, 2012; Pavlova, 2013). In the current analyses, we comprehensively incorporate each of these conceptualizations of environmental attitudes.

Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes

Our primary aim is to test how environmental attitudes vary with age, from childhood through emerging adulthood. Some cross-sectional studies have suggested an adolescent dip in environmental beliefs, affect, and behavior (Baierl et al., 2022; sample age 12-18), sustainability consciousness (Olsson & Gericke, 2016; sample age 12-19), and preference for natural (compared to human-made) settings more generally (Kaplan & Kaplan, 2002; sample age 8-19). Together, these studies suggest a normative age trend by which pro-environmental attitudes decline during middle adolescence (i.e., at around age 15-16) but bounce back in late adolescence (i.e., at around age 18-19).

What might account for this putative adolescent dip in environmental attitudes? One possibility is that adolescents feel limited in their ability to meaningfully contribute to society, potentially leading to a sense of helplessness, apathy, or a tendency to disengage from environmental issues altogether (Crandon et al., 2022; Ojala, 2022; te Brinke et al.,

2022). Another possibility is that current educational practices fail to persuasively convey to adolescents how pro-environmental engagement is relevant to them personally, or compatible with their developmentally salient needs and motives (Olsson & Gericke, 2016). For example, environmental education that tells adolescents how to engage in pro-environmental behavior may inadvertently convey that sustainability is for “obedient followers” rather than for “independent frontrunners.” As such, it may fail to resonate with adolescents’ developmentally salient needs, such as for autonomy or respect (Dahl et al., 2018; Thomaes et al., 2023; Yeager et al., 2018). Indeed, environmental education programs sometimes prove less effective among adolescents than among children (Liefländer et al., 2013; Świątkowski et al., 2024).

Although some studies have suggested that by late adolescence, environmental attitudes tend to bounce back and become more favorable again, evidence for such a rebound is mixed. One longitudinal study reported a decline in pro-environmental attitudes starting in early adolescence and persisting into late adolescence (Otto et al., 2019; sample age 7-17). Similar downward trends from late childhood through late adolescence have been observed for closely related phenomena such as connectedness to nature and pro-environmental behavior (Krettenauer, 2017; sample age 12-20; Krettenauer et al., 2020; sample age 9-21; Negev et al., 2008; sample age 12-19; Wray-Lake et al., 2017; sample age 8-20), as well as more distally related phenomena such as social responsibility values (Wray-Lake et al., 2016; sample age 10-18). By contrast, studies on the associated phenomena of prosocial behavior and civic engagement have found normative age-related increases (rather than adolescent dips or declines), attributed to adolescents’ growing cognitive and socio-emotional competences (e.g., abstract reasoning, perspective taking; Crone & Achterberg, 2022; Grütter & Buchmann, 2022; Sweijen et al., 2024; Wray-Lake et al., 2014).

Thus, the empirical evidence for normative age trends in environmental attitudes (and related constructs) remains equivocal. One possible reason, we propose, lies in methodological differences between studies. In particular, prior research has relied on samples of various (and sometimes narrow) age ranges, limiting their comparability. Moreover, studies have focused on diverse conceptualizations of environmental attitudes, which may show divergent developmental pathways (Cruz & Manata, 2020). In our analysis, we address these issues by systematically investigating age trends in environmental attitudes across a broad age range (ages 8 to 25), and by including data reflecting diverse conceptualizations of environmental attitudes.

Historical Time Trends in Environmental Attitudes

A secondary aim of our research is to explore whether or how adolescents' levels of environmental attitudes have changed over recent decades. There is reason to believe that adolescents' environmental attitudes may have become more favorable. The impacts of climate change and environmental degradation have become increasingly visible and tangible over the past decade (IPCC, 2023). Relatedly, climate change and environmental degradation have received increasing attention in the media and in educational settings, potentially fostering greater awareness and concern (Chen et al., 2019; Pianta & Sisco, 2020; Sampei & Aoyagi-Usui, 2009; Schmidt et al., 2013). Together, these developments suggest that environmental attitudes may have increased in recent years across age groups, including adolescents.

At the same time, environmental challenges such as climate change will disproportionately impact the lives of today's youth, more than the lives of today's older generations (IPCC, 2023; Thierry et al., 2021; UNICEF, 2021). This is especially true for young people living in climate-vulnerable regions, such as many countries in the Global South, where risks of exposure to climate-related hazards (e.g., heatwaves, floods, and

storms) are heightened, while resources to cope with their socio-economic, infrastructural, and health impacts tend to be more limited (UNICEF, 2021). Finally, youth climate movements such as Fridays For Future have mobilized unprecedented numbers of young people, inspiring youth worldwide to engage with climate change (de Moor et al., 2020; Marris, 2019; Wahlström et al., 2020).

Together, these societal developments may be reflected in increasingly favorable environmental attitudes among young people, especially in recent years (Hartmann & Preisendörfer, 2021). Consistent with that possibility, a recent survey among Swedish late adolescents found a sharp rise in climate worry (i.e., an emotion that is correlated with favorable environmental attitudes; Bouman et al., 2020; Ojala et al., 2021; Verplanken & Roy, 2013) from 2010 to 2020 (Wullenkord et al., 2023). Similarly, in a four-year longitudinal study, two cohorts of adolescents and young adults (ages 12 and 18, respectively, at the study start) displayed similar developmental patterns in nature connectedness and pro-environmental behavior, suggesting that historical time—more than age per se—accounted for these patterns (Krettenauer et al., 2024). Building on this work, the current research examines historical time effects on environmental attitudes across a broader time span.

The Present Study

In this meta-analysis, we synthesize individual participant data from studies that assessed environmental attitudes among youth to compute precise estimates of age and historical time effects (Riley et al., 2010). We adopt a comprehensive definition of adolescence as a developmental period that starts with puberty and extends to approximately age 25, thus including “emerging adulthood,” a developmental period characterized by continuing biological maturation and social role transitions (Arnett, 2000; Sawyer et al., 2018). Including participants up to this age allows us to examine the possibility that potential rebounds in environmental attitudes occur only during this later developmental phase (i.e.,

18-25 years), which could explain why prior work that sampled younger youth found no evidence for such a rebound. We were able to include data collected from the early 2000s onwards (when two key environmental attitudes measures were introduced to the literature; Bogner & Wiseman, 2006; Dunlap et al., 2000), thus enabling us to investigate potential changes in young people's environmental attitudes over the past two decades.

Methods

Transparency and Openness

Our study was approved by the faculty ethics review board at Utrecht University (#20-621). We preregistered our study protocol following PRISMA-IPD guidelines (Stewart et al., 2015) on Open Science Framework (OSF) prior to study selection (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/FW9HU>). Codebooks and analysis code are also available on OSF. Due to ethical and legal restrictions associated with the original datasets, some of which were non-anonymous, it is not possible to make supporting data available.

Eligibility Criteria

We considered studies eligible if they assessed environmental attitudes with one or more of the following three measures: the revised New Ecological Paradigm scale (NEP; Dunlap et al., 2000), the 2 Major Environmental Values scale (2-MEV; as published in Bogner & Wiseman, 2006), or the Sustainability Consciousness Questionnaire (SCQ; Gericke et al., 2019).

The NEP is the most widely used scale for assessing environmental attitudes (Bernstein, 2020; Hawcroft & Milfont, 2010). To ensure comparability across studies, we only included studies that used the revised NEP (Dunlap et al., 2000), rather than the original scale (Dunlap & Van Liere, 1978), or modifications that were developed for children only (e.g., Izadpanahi & Tucker, 2018; Manoli et al., 2007). The 2-MEV is a widely used measure of environmental attitudes that has been developed specifically for adolescents (Bogner &

Wiseman, 2006). The SCQ assesses sustainability consciousness, a multidimensional concept reflecting awareness of social, economic, and environmental sustainability as intertwined issues (Kopnina, 2012; Pavlova, 2013). We did not select studies that used other measures, as they have been rarely used with adolescents (e.g., Milfont & Duckitt, 2010), or contain items considered outdated (e.g., Weigel & Weigel, 1978; Cruz & Manata, 2020).

We included studies only if the English full text was available or made available by the author(s) upon request, and if the study sample included participants aged 25 years or younger. We excluded studies if environmental attitudes were assessed solely after some form of intervention (e.g., educational program). At the participant level, we excluded participants older than 25 years, as well as assessments of environmental attitudes that had been obtained after intervention.

Study Identification

We conducted forward citation searching (Briscoe et al., 2020) using the citation indexes of Scopus and Web of Science to identify relevant study reports up to March 12, 2024 (an initial search, up to May 8, 2021, was updated to include more recent data). Key citations were selected to identify studies using the NEP (i.e., Dunlap et al., 2000), 2-MEV (i.e., Bogner & Wiseman, 2006), and SCQ (i.e., Gericke et al., 2019; Olsson & Gericke, 2016). We also searched for unpublished dissertations in the Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD) database. As citation searching is not possible within the NDLTD, we conducted the following keyword search: “environmental attitudes” OR “environmental concern” OR “new ecological paradigm” OR “environmental values” OR “sustainability consciousness”. We limited the keyword search to English-language reports published from 2000 onwards, as the earliest measure selected for our study was published in that year. Finally, although we did not set out to do this, we obtained a few additional (unpublished, more recent) datasets through author correspondence.

Study Selection

A flow diagram of the study selection process is presented in Figure 1. Study selection proceeded in two steps in which one coder first screened titles and abstracts for eligibility, and then proceeded to screen the full text of the remaining study reports. A second independent coder screened 10% of abstracts (92% overlap in decisions) and full texts (88% overlap). Disagreements were resolved through discussion and the eligibility criteria were refined accordingly.

We initially included a total of 556 study reports that used the NEP. To ensure feasibility, we decided to add a third selection step. A coder rated study reports that used the NEP in terms of whether (a) they had included all fifteen NEP items, (b) 40-60% of the sample was female, and (c) either the sample age range spanned at least 2 years and the range maximum was 25 years or the sample mean age was below 25 years (1 = *yes*, 0 = *no*). Based on these additional selection criteria, we sought individual participant data for 67 study reports (i.e., 12.1% of all available study reports that used the NEP), and excluded the remaining study reports.

Figure 1*Search and Selection of Study Records*

Note. IPD = individual participant data.

^a Including 9 unpublished datasets.

^b For feasibility, we only sought individual participant data for NEP records that were eligible based on the additional, stricter eligibility criteria that records (a) included all 15 NEP items, (b) sampled 40-60% female participants, and (c) included an age range of two years

minimum, with a maximum age of 25 years or a mean age under 25 years. We also did not seek individual participant data for reports that only reported age in categories (except for primary and secondary school grades).

Data Collection Process and Data Items

We extracted study characteristics (i.e., study design, preregistration, study country, year of data collection) and sample characteristics (i.e., sample size, age or grade mean and range, percentage of girls, percentage cultural or ethnic minority, used measure of environmental attitudes) from included study reports. We requested anonymized, raw individual participant data (i.e., age, sex, item-level scores on environmental attitudes) from the corresponding authors of the included study reports. Corresponding authors signed a data sharing agreement specifying ethical and ownership issues. Queries were resolved in collaboration with corresponding authors to ensure individual participant data integrity.

Data Items

Environmental Attitudes. The primary study outcomes are environmental attitudes as measured by one of the three measures listed below. The full measures are included in the Supplemental Material (Table S1).

Revised New Ecological Paradigm Scale. The revised NEP (Dunlap et al., 2000) measures environmental attitudes or concern. It uses items concerning cognitions about humanity's relationship with nature that reflect the level of endorsement of an ecocentric new ecological paradigm (e.g., the fragility of nature's balance, the possibility of an ecological crisis). It consists of 15 items that are rated along a five-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*). Sample items include "Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist" and "If things continue on their present course, we will soon experience a major ecological catastrophe". After reverse coding negatively worded items, we computed a

single mean scale score, with higher scores indicating more favorable environmental attitudes.

2 Major Environmental Values Scale. The 2-MEV (Bogner & Wiseman, 2006) measures environmental attitudes on two orthogonal subscales: an ecocentric subscale that reflects environmental preservation (i.e., preservation) and an anthropocentric subscale that reflects the utilization of natural resources (i.e., utilization). Each subscale consists of 10 items that are rated along a five-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*). Sample items include “We must set aside areas to protect endangered species” (for preservation) and “Humans have the right to change nature as they see fit” (for utilization). We computed mean scores for both subscales, with higher scores on the preservation subscale indicating more favorable environmental attitudes, and higher scores on the utilization subscale indicating less favorable environmental attitudes.

Sustainability Consciousness Questionnaire. The SCQ (Olsson et al., 2016; Gericke et al., 2019) measures awareness of and experience with environmental, economic, and societal sustainability. It consists of 50 items that measure sustainability knowingness, attitudes, and behavior. Items are rated along a five-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*). Sample items include “Wiping out poverty in the world is necessary for sustainable development”, “I think that we need stricter laws and regulations to protect the environment” and “I show the same respect to men and women, boys and girls”. After reverse coding negatively worded items, we computed mean subscale scores for environmental consciousness specifically (including 17 items, as reported in Olsson & Gericke, 2016) and for overall sustainability consciousness (including all 50 items, as recommended by Gericke et al., 2019). Higher scale scores indicate more sustainability consciousness.

Participant Age. We analyzed participant age in years. If missing (for 13.7% of the datasets, including 22.5% of the total number of participants), we approximated participants' age by taking the median of the typical age range for the reported school grade(s) in the pertaining country where the study was conducted.

Year of Data Collection. We analyzed year of data collection as reported in the study reports or as provided by the corresponding authors. If unavailable (for 43.8% of the datasets, including 12.5% of the total number of participants), we approximated year of data collection by subtracting 2 years from the study report's publication year.

Analysis Plan

We conducted analyses in R 4.4.0 (R Core Team, 2024).

Preliminary Analyses

We handled missing data on environmental attitude items by substituting missing items with a participants' mean score from the other items (i.e., person mean substitution). We also explored the possibility of multilevel multiple imputation, but the pertaining models did not converge (see the Supplemental Material for more information). There were no items that substantially reduced the reliability of the environmental attitude scales. Missingness was dependent on dataset (i.e., in some datasets, certain items were missing for all participants because they were not administered).

Primary Analyses

We ran separate analyses for each environmental attitudes scale (i.e., NEP, 2-MEV preservation, 2-MEV utilization, overall SCQ, and environmental SCQ). To test age trends, we regressed environmental attitudes on age; to test historical time trends, we regressed environmental attitudes on year of data collection, while controlling for participant age. We mean-centered our predictor variables.

We conducted our analyses stepwise. First, we specified a series of random-intercept multilevel models using the `lme4` (Bates et al., 2024) package to account for the nesting of participants (level 1) in datasets (level 2), using restricted maximum likelihood (REML) estimation. Specifically, we fitted an (a) intercept-only model, including a random intercept but no predictor; (b) a linear model, including age (or year of data collection and age) as predictor; (c) a quadratic model, adding quadratic age (or year of data collection) as additional predictor; and (d) a general additive model (GAM) including age (or year of data collection and age) as predictor using the `mgcv` (Wood, 2023) package.

GAMs allow for estimating a smooth nonlinear function by combining multiple thin-plate splines, thus allowing trends in environmental attitudes to take a different shape across different levels of age (or year of data collection; Levelt et al., 2025). The points where the trend changes shape (if any) are identified by “knots”. We used the default upper limit of 10 knots in our models (this limit is not very important though, as GAMs reduce the number of knots during model fitting through penalization, eliminating unnecessary fluctuations that do not substantially improve model fit; Wood et al., 2014).

Second, we compared the models in terms of their fit (as indicated by a higher log likelihood value) and balance between increased fit and model complexity (as indicated by lower deviance, AIC, and BIC values). As recommended (Zuur et al., 2009), we re-estimated our models with maximum likelihood (ML) estimation for model comparisons. Finally, we obtained the estimates of and visualized the best fitting model.

Sensitivity and Exploratory Analyses

We tested whether inferences based on the best fitting models changed when (a) controlling for participant and study characteristics (i.e., gender, study design, sample size, scale reliability, and missingness), (b) downweighing the influence of outliers (using the `robustlmm` package for robust multilevel modeling; Koller, 2016), (c) and replacing our

proxy for year of data collection of publication year by -3 years (rather than -2 years). We also explored to what extent scales were psychometrically equivalent across age groups using measurement invariance analysis (see Supplemental Material for more information). Finally, we performed non-preregistered exploratory moderation analyses, testing whether age trends in environmental attitudes were moderated by gender (female versus male; <0.1% did not self-identify as boy or girl; gender was missing for 1.4% of participants) and world region (Global North [93.5% of participants] versus Global South [6.4% of participants; 0.1% missing], as indicated by a Human Development Index >.80; United Nations Development Programme, 2025).

Results

Study Pool and Participants

We obtained individual participant data from 68 study reports based on 73 datasets, including a total of 62,204 participants. Participants ranged in age from 8 to 25 years ($M = 14.27$, $SD = 3.46$), and 49.6% was female. The data were collected between 2005 and 2024 across 27 countries. Data were mostly based on cross-sectional designs (90.4% of datasets, 5.5% missing). Therefore, in the few cases of a longitudinal design (4.1% of datasets), we included the first wave only. Participants were mostly from Europe (72.8%) and North America (17.4%), but also from Asia (7.9%), Africa (1.2%), South America (0.4%), and Oceania (0.2%). Participants reported on the 2-MEV (71.6%), the NEP (30.4%), or the SCQ (10.5%), with some datasets including more than one measure. Descriptives for each measure are reported in Table 1. Details for each dataset are reported in Table S2-S3 in the Supplemental Material.

Table 1*Descriptives for the Environmental Attitudes Measures*

Descriptives	NEP	2-MEV	SCQ
<i>N</i> datasets	44	24	8
Year of data collection range	2005–2022	2005–2024	2013–2021
<i>N</i> participants ^a	18,939	44,523	6,508
Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	8–25 (15.65, 5.04)	8–25 (12.94, 2.15)	8–25 (14.68, 3.38)
Gender frequency (%)			
Female	9,261 (48.9)	22,113 (49.7)	3,231 (49.6)
Male	8,941 (47.2)	21,629 (48.6)	3,225 (49.6)
Continent frequency (%)			
Europe	5,237 (27.7)	36,198 (81.3)	4,704 (72.3)
North America	10,719 (56.6)	6,966 (15.6)	-
Asia	2,744 (14.5)	379 (0.9)	1,804 (27.7)
Africa	206 (1.1)	557 (1.3)	-
South America	33 (0.2)	186 (0.4)	-
Oceania	-	153 (0.3)	-

Note.

^aDuring our search update, we obtained a relatively large number of participants reporting on the 2-MEV.

Preliminary Analyses

Table 2 presents subscale descriptives and correlations for the study variables. The 2-MEV preservation and utilization subscales were weakly negatively correlated ($r = -.17$, 95% CI [-.19, -.15]). The SCQ overall and environmental subscales were strongly positively correlated ($r = .85$, 95% CI [.84, .86]).

Table 2*Scale Descriptives and Correlations for the Study Variables*

Variable	α	M	SD	Range	Correlations	
					Participant age	Year of data collection
1. NEP	.76	3.55	0.55	1-5	-.08*	-.19*
					[-.10, -.07]	[-.21, -.17]
2. 2-MEV preservation	.77	3.76	0.78	1-5	-.05*	-.01
					[-.07, -.04]	[-.03, .01]
3. 2-MEV utilization	.75	2.53	0.74	1-5	-.01*	.03*
					[-.02, -.00]	[.02, .04]
4. SCQ overall	.91	3.94	0.49	1-5	-.16*	.23*
					[-.18, -.13]	[.20, .25]
5. SCQ environmental	.76	3.83	0.55	1-5	-.09*	.17*
					[-.12, -.07]	[.15, .20]

Note. α represents the Cronbach's alpha across all datasets using that measure. Values in square brackets indicate the 95% confidence interval for each correlation.

* indicates $p < .01$.

Primary Analyses

Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes

We specified—for each environmental attitudes scale separately—a series of random-intercept multilevel models with environmental attitudes regressed on age. For all scales, the quadratic model fitted our data best (Table 3).

NEP. For the NEP, the quadratic model ($R^2 = 24.5\%$, intercept NEP scores = 3.42, $SE = 0.06$) showed that increasing age predicted a small increase in endorsement of the new ecological paradigm that peaks at age 21 and then levels off (linear effect: $b = 0.01$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = .12$, $p < .001$; quadratic effect: $b < -0.01$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = -.03$, $p < .001$; Figure 2, panel A).

2-MEV. For the 2-MEV preservation subscale, where higher scores reflect more favorable environmental attitudes, the quadratic model ($R^2 = 13.1\%$, intercept preservation scores = 3.68, $SE = 0.11$) showed that increasing age predicted a medium decrease in endorsement of nature preservation until age 19, followed by a small increase (linear effect: $b = -0.09$, $SE = 0.01$, $\beta = -.37$, $p < .001$; quadratic effect: $b = 0.01$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = .17$, $p < .001$; Figure 2, Panel B). For the 2-MEV utilization subscale, where higher scores reflect *less* (not more) favorable environmental attitudes, the quadratic model ($R^2 = 9.1\%$, intercept utilization scores = 2.66, $SE = 0.15$) showed that increasing age predicted a small increase in endorsement of nature utilization that accelerates slightly but non-significantly from age 7 onward (linear effect: $b = 0.01$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.04$, $p < .001$; quadratic effect: $b < 0.01$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = .02$, $p = .089$; Figure 2, panel C).

SCQ. For the overall SCQ scale, where higher scores reflect more sustainability consciousness, the quadratic model ($R^2 = 11.7\%$, intercept sustainability consciousness scores = 3.41, $SE = 0.29$) showed that increasing age predicted a small decrease in knowingness, attitudes, and behaviors concerning environmental, social, and economic sustainability until

age 16, followed by a small increase (linear effect: $b = -0.02$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = -0.16$, $p < .001$; quadratic effect: $b = 0.01$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.19$, $p < .001$; Figure 2, Panel D). For the environmental SCQ subscale, where higher scores reflect more environmental sustainability consciousness, the quadratic model ($R^2 = 7.5\%$, intercept environmental sustainability consciousness scores = 3.26, $SE = 0.26$) showed that increasing age predicted a small decrease in knowingness, attitudes, and behaviors concerning environmental sustainability until 15 years, followed by a small increase (linear effect: $b < -0.00$, $SE = 0.26$, $\beta = -0.02$, $p = 0.350$; quadratic effect: $b = 0.01$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.19$, $p < .001$; Figure 2, Panel E).

Summary. Taken together, our analyses show that age trends in environmental attitudes vary markedly depending on how these attitudes are conceptualized. Overall, effects were small in magnitude. Reflecting a strengthening of environmental attitudes with age, young people's endorsement of the new ecological paradigm (i.e., the NEP) increased with age, only leveling off somewhat by late adolescence. Conversely, reflecting a weakening of environmental attitudes with age, young people's endorsement of nature utilization (i.e., the 2-MEV utilization subscale) increased with age. Finally, reflecting an adolescent dip in environmental attitudes, both young people's endorsement of nature preservation (i.e., the 2-MEV preservation subscale) and overall and environmental sustainability consciousness (i.e., the SCQ), initially decreased and then increased with age (although the exact timing of this dip differed somewhat across measures).

Historical Time Trends in Environmental Attitudes

We specified—for each environmental attitudes scale separately—a series of random-intercept multilevel models with environmental attitudes regressed on year of data collection, controlling for age. Linear models fitted the data best for most scales (except for a better fit of a quadratic model for the NEP scale; Table S4), but year of data collection did not significantly predict environmental attitudes for any of the scales (see Supplemental Material

for details). Thus, we found no evidence for historical time trends in adolescents' environmental attitudes.

Sensitivity Analyses

Controlling for Covariates

We tested whether inferences based on the best fitting models changed when controlling for participant and study characteristics (i.e., gender, study design, sample size, scale reliability, and missingness). Our inferences of age trends in environmental attitudes did not change when controlling for covariates—that is, trend directions remained the same, although in some cases they dropped below conventional significance levels (Table S6). Importantly, for all scales, gender was a significant predictor of environmental attitudes, such that girls held more favorable environmental attitudes than boys. Also, our inferences of historical time trends in environmental attitudes generally did not change when controlling for covariates (although models for SCQ scales failed to converge; Table S7). The only exception was that quadratic year of data collection became a small but significant negative predictor in the quadratic model for the NEP scale. Again, gender was a significant predictor of environmental attitudes in all models testing for historical time trends.

Downweighing Outlier Influence

Our inferences of age (Table S8) and historical time trends (Table S9) in environmental attitudes did not change when downweighing the influence of outliers.

Adjusting Proxy for Year of Data Collection

Inferences mostly did not change when replacing our proxy for year of data collection of publication year -2 years by -3 years (Table S10). Again, the only exception was that quadratic year of data collection became a small but significant negative predictor in the quadratic model for the NEP scale.

Exploratory Analyses

We examined to what extent the scales were psychometrically equivalent across age. The results of these measurement invariance analyses suggest that young people of different ages may interpret the scale items differently (see Supplemental Material for details).

Non-Preregistered Exploratory Analyses

We further explored whether age trends in environmental attitudes were moderated by gender (girls versus boys) and world region (Global North versus Global South). These analyses showed that gender moderated age trends for most scales (except for the 2-MEV preservation scale; Table S11). Initial age-related increases in endorsement of the new ecological paradigm (NEP scale) were less steep for males and leveled off to a lesser extent; initial age-related increases in endorsement of nature utilization (2-MEV utilization scale) were less steep for males but accelerated more; initial age-related decreases in endorsement of overall sustainability consciousness (overall SCQ scale) were steeper for males; and initial age-related decreases in endorsement of environmental sustainability consciousness applied only to males (Figure S2).

Additionally, exploratory analyses showed that world region moderated age trends for both 2-MEV scales (but not for the NEP scale, and we did not perform these moderation analyses for SCQ scales as these data relied exclusively on Global North countries; Table S12). Strikingly, age-related trends in endorsement of nature preservation and utilization showed opposite patterns in the Global North and the Global South, with environmental attitudes generally becoming less favorable with age in the Global North yet more favorable with age in the Global South (Figure 3).

Table 3*Model Comparisons for Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes*

Model	AIC	BIC	Log likelihood	Deviance
NEP ($N = 18,939$)				
Null	26046	26069	-13020	26040
Linear	26040	26072	-13016	26032
Quadratic	26030	26069	-13010	26020
General additive model	30221	30312	-15099	5462
2-MEV preservation ($N = 14,848$)				
Null	33088	33111	-16541	33082
Linear	32909	32939	-16450	32901
Quadratic	32825	32863	-16407	32815
General additive model	34128	34208	-17053	8646
2-MEV utilization ($N = 44,519$)				
Null	95257	95283	-47625	95251
Linear	95241	95276	-47616	95233
Quadratic	95240	95283	-47615	95230
General additive model	98738	98840	-49357	23936
SCQ overall ($N = 6,507$)				
Null	8481	8502	-4238	8475
Linear	8457	8485	-4225	8449

Quadratic	8367	8401	-4179	8357
General additive model	8577	8644	-4278	1419
<hr/>				
SCQ environmental ($N = 6,504$)				
Null	10300	10321	-5147	10294
Linear	10298	10325	-5145	10290
Quadratic	10210	10244	-5100	10200
General additive model	10235	10306	-5107	1831

Note. Bolded values indicate the best fit. The sample size difference between the 2-MEV preservation and utilization scales is mostly caused by one large dataset for which we obtained utilization but not preservation scores.

Figure 2*Modeled Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes*

Note. For green (versus red) trends, higher values reflect more (versus less) favorable environmental attitudes. Panel A models quadratic age differences in NEP scores. Panel B and C model quadratic age differences in 2-MEV preservation and utilization scores, respectively. Panel D and E model quadratic age differences in overall and environmental SCQ scores, respectively.

Figure 3

Modeled Age by World Region Interactions in Environmental Attitudes

Note. Panel A models quadratic age differences in NEP scores (moderation was not significant). Panel B and C model quadratic age differences in 2-MEV preservation and utilization scores, respectively. We did not perform these moderation analyses for SCQ scales as these data relied exclusively on Global North countries.

Discussion

Climate change and its consequences will disproportionately impact the future lives of today's young generations (IPCC, 2023; Thiery et al., 2021). We synthesized data of 62,204 young people from 73 international datasets to provide the most comprehensive estimates to date of how their environmental attitudes vary across age from childhood through emerging adulthood (i.e., 8 to 25 years) and recent historical time (i.e., 2005 to 2024). We scrutinized the evidence for an 'adolescent dip' in young people's environmental attitudes—that is, the possibility that adolescents think, feel, and act less favorably toward the natural environment than both children and adults. Prior work has found some, but inconsistent, support for this pattern (e.g., Baierl et al., 2022; Krettenauer, 2017; Olsson & Gericke, 2016; Otto et al., 2019).

Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes Vary Across Conceptualizations

We found no evidence of an overall adolescent dip in environmental attitudes. Rather, we found that age trends in environmental attitudes depend on how these attitudes are conceptualized. Specifically, reflecting a strengthening of environmental attitudes with age, young people showed an age-related linear increase (which levelled off by late adolescence) in their endorsement of an ecological worldview, rooted in the fundamental belief that nature has inherent value of its own (as measured with the NEP scale; Dunlap et al., 2000). Conversely, reflecting a weakening of environmental attitudes with age, young people showed an age-related linear increase in their endorsement of nature utilization for human benefits (e.g., depleting resources for infrastructure construction or food production, as measured with the 2-MEV utilization scale; Bogner & Wiseman, 2006). Finally, we did find an adolescent dip in environmental attitudes as assessed with the 2-MEV preservation scale (Bogner & Wiseman, 2006) and the SCQ scales (Olsson et al., 2016; Gericke et al., 2019). Young people showed a mid-adolescent dip in their endorsement of nature conservation and

protection (e.g., setting aside areas to protect endangered species, saving water and energy) and in their overall and environmental sustainability consciousness.

Taken together, our evidence suggests that different aspects of environmental attitudes follow differentiated age trends. Specifically, cognitive aspects of environmental attitudes (i.e., ecological worldviews, as measured with the NEP scale) may gradually increase from late childhood to emerging adulthood, likely reflecting adolescents' growing societal engagement as well as advances in cognitive (e.g., abstract reasoning) and socioemotional (e.g., perspective taking) development (Crone et al., 2024; Grütter & Buchmann, 2022; Wray-Lake et al., 2014). This same normative development may also underlie the (seemingly paradoxical) increase in adolescents' endorsement of nature utilization (as measured with the 2-MEV scale): as adolescents develop a more complex understanding of human-nature relations, they may adopt more nuanced positions toward environmental issues than they do at a younger age (Krettenauer, 2017).

Finally, the adolescent dip in endorsement of nature preservation (as measured with the 2-MEV scale) and sustainability consciousness (as measured with the SCQ scale) may reflect that, with age, adolescents increasingly disengage with pro-environmental behavior (which the 2-MEV preservation subscale and SCQ scales emphasize more than the other scales, e.g., "I always switch the light off when I don't need it"; Spitzer et al., 2024; te Brinke et al., 2022). Accordingly, an adolescent dip in pro-environmental affect and behavior might signal more than that (mid-)adolescents do not care about environmental issues—it may also signal that they need improved opportunities to help them see how pro-environmental engagement can be both personally meaningful and effective to address environmental issues (Pluess, 2024; Spitzer et al., 2024; Thomaes et al., 2023). Overall, our findings highlight that environmental attitudes show distinct and diverging age-related trends, depending on how they are conceptualized and operationalized.

Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes Are Not Universal

Our analysis also suggests that age trends in environmental attitudes are not universal. For example, we found exploratory evidence for distinct age trends across genders, generally suggesting greater age-related strengthening of environmental attitudes for females compared to males. One explanation for this may be that female adolescents tend to view engagement with sustainability as more personally meaningful than males (Grapsas et al., 2024). We also found exploratory evidence for distinct age trends across world regions (i.e., for endorsement of nature preservation and utilization), suggesting age-related weakening of environmental attitudes in the Global North but strengthening in the Global South. One potential explanation is that young people in the Global South are increasingly impacted by climate change hazards with age, more so than their peers in the Global North (Hickman et al., 2021; IPCC, 2023; Thiery et al., 2021). Indeed, public support for climate policies is generally stronger in the Global South compared to the Global North (Bretter & Schulz, 2025). Together, our findings show that age trends in environmental attitudes are heterogeneous, making universal claims unwarranted.

Environmental Attitudes Are Stable Across Historical Time

We found no evidence that young people have come to hold more favorable environmental attitudes in recent years. We did anticipate such a historical time trend, given increased coverage of climate change by media and in educational settings, growing visibility of its consequences, and the rise of youth climate movements in recent years (Schmidt et al., 2013; Thiery et al., 2021; Wahlström et al., 2020). One reason, we speculate, may be that the measures that we analyzed primarily assess attitudes toward the natural environment in general (e.g., appreciation for nature and biodiversity, resource depletion, rights of non-human species; Bogner & Wiseman, 2006; Dunlap et al., 2000), rather than toward climate change specifically. While concern for climate change among young people may have grown

in recent years (Wullenkord et al., 2023), attitudes toward the natural environment in general have remained relatively stable.

Strengths, Limitations, and Future Directions

This research provides the most precise and comprehensive estimates to date of age and historical time trends in young people's environmental attitudes. The individual participant data approach that we used enabled a more fine-grained analysis than traditional meta-analytic methods, and offered nuanced insights in age-related patterns of environmental attitudes from childhood through emerging adulthood (Riley et al., 2010). Our analysis overcomes several limitations of prior research. First, the wide age range of the sample we included (8 to 25 years) allowed us to explore potential shifts in environmental attitudes that could have occurred as early as late childhood, or as late as emerging adulthood. Second, by including data based on multiple scales, we were able to compare trends across conceptualizations of environmental attitudes. Third, the data that we obtained spans nearly two decades (i.e., 2005 to 2024) and thus reflects young people's environmental attitudes across a period in which public attention for environmental issues has risen sharply (de Moor et al., 2020; Marris, 2019; Wahlström et al., 2020).

Our analysis also has limitations. First, it is quite common in this field to adapt environmental attitudes measures for use with specific samples (e.g., child samples, samples from various countries), and so we needed to make decisions to ensure comparability across datasets (Cruz & Manata, 2020; Hawcroft & Milfont, 2010). This required balancing excluding studies that relied on heavily adapted or shortened measures, while accepting some heterogeneity by including studies that relied on measures that used minor item rephrasing or deletion. Also, our measurement invariance analyses indicate that scale interpretation may differ across age, which may have colored our estimations of age trends (Chen, 2007). Such differences are theoretically expected given developmental changes in cognitive and social-

emotional competencies (e.g., abstract reasoning, perspective taking) across the broad age range of participants we included (Crone et al., 2024; Grütter & Buchmann, 2022; Wray-Lake et al., 2014). Following others (Rohrer & Paulewicz, 2025), we suggest that these differences are substantively informative: future research could examine how and why young people's understanding of environmental attitudes evolves with age.

Second, our analyses were cross-sectional and did not allow for testing within-person development in environmental attitudes over time, nor the mechanisms that underlie this development. Future longitudinal research could test, for example, to what extent the development of cognitive and socioemotional capabilities (Grütter & Buchmann, 2022; Wray-Lake et al., 2014), the perceived relevance of sustainability for adolescents' motives (Thomaes et al., 2023), and perceived opportunities to contribute (Spitzer et al., 2023; te Brinke et al., 2022), drive the development of environmental attitudes. Finally, while we obtained data from five continents, participants were still predominantly from countries in Europe and North America—i.e., parts of the world that have traditionally been overrepresented in psychological science (Henrich et al., 2010; Rad et al., 2018). As such, we urge caution in generalizing our findings globally, especially because young people in the Global South are disproportionately exposed to and worried about climate change hazards, and may show unique age shifts in environmental attitudes (Hickman et al., 2021; IPCC, 2023; Thiery et al., 2021). Continued international collaboration is needed to map and understand the environmental engagement of youth worldwide.

Conclusion

By synthesizing data of 62,204 young people from 73 international datasets, we found evidence that young people's environmental attitudes have remained largely stable over the past two decades. While we found an adolescent dip in sustainability consciousness and endorsement of nature preservation, this pattern was not universal. Instead, age trends varied

systematically depending on how environmental attitudes are conceptualized, as well as on individual and contextual characteristics.

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Supplemental Material

Methods

Table S1

Full Item List of Each of the Measures of Environmental Attitudes

Measure	Item
NEP	1 We are approaching the limit of the number of people the Earth can support
	2* Humans have the right to modify the natural environment to suit their needs
	3 When humans interfere with nature it often produces disastrous consequences
	4* Human ingenuity will ensure that we do not make the Earth unlivable
	5 Humans are seriously abusing the environment
	6* The Earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them
	7 Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist
	8* The balance of nature is strong enough to cope with the impacts of modern industrial nations
	9 Despite our special abilities, humans are still subject to the laws of nature
	10* The so-called “ecological crisis” facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated
	11 The Earth is like a spaceship with very limited room and resources
	12* Humans were meant to rule over the rest of nature
	13 The balance of nature is very delicate and easily upset
	14* Humans will eventually learn enough about how nature works to be able to control it
	15 If things continue on their present course, we will soon experience a major ecological catastrophe

Measure		Item
2-MEV preservation	19	It upsets me to see the countryside taken over by building sites
	14	I enjoy trips to the countryside
	11	Humankind will die out if we don't live in tune with nature
	22	Society will continue to solve even the biggest environmental problems
	15	Sitting at the edge of a pond watching dragonflies in flight is enjoyable
	3	I save water by taking a shower instead of a bath (in order to spare water)
	4	I always switch the light off when I don't need it
	20	We must set aside areas to protect endangered species
	17	It is interesting to know what kinds of creatures live in ponds or rivers
	18	Dirty industrial smoke from chimneys makes me angry
2-MEV utilization	42	Worrying about the environment often holds up development projects
	26	We need to clear forests in order to grow crops
	36	Our planet has unlimited resources
	37	Nature is always able to restore itself
	40	We must build more roads so people can travel to the countryside
	41	Only plants and animals of economical importance need to be protected
	24	Humans have the right to change nature as they see fit
	43	People worry too much about pollution
	44	Human beings are more important than other creatures
	30	We should remove garden weeds to help beautiful flowers grow

Measure	Item
SCQ knowingness	k1 Economic development is necessary for sustainable development
	k2 Improving peoples chances for a long and healthy life contributes to sustainable development
	<i>k3 Reducing water consumption is necessary for sustainable development</i>
	<i>k4* Preserving nature is not necessary for sustainable development</i>
	k5 A culture where conflicts are resolved peacefully through discussion is necessary for sustainable development
	<i>k7 Sustainable development demands that we humans reduce all sorts of waste</i>
	k8 People who exercise their democratic rights are necessary for sustainable development (for example, they vote in elections, involve themselves in social issues, express their opinions)
	k9 Reinforcing girls and women's rights and increasing equality around the world is necessary for sustainable development
	k10 Respecting human rights is necessary for sustainable development
	k11 To achieve sustainable development, all the people in the world must have access to good education
	k12 sustainable development requires that companies act responsibly towards their employees, customers and suppliers
	<i>k14 Preserving the variety of living creatures is necessary for sustainable development (preserving biological diversity)</i>
	k15 Having respect for other cultures is necessary for sustainable development
	k16 Sustainable development requires a fair distribution of goods and services among people in the world
	k17 Wiping out poverty in the world is necessary for sustainable development
	<i>k18 Sustainable development requires a shift to renewable natural resources</i>

Measure	Item
SCQ attitudes	k19 Sustainable development demands that people understand how the economy functions
	k20 For sustainable development, major infectious diseases such as HIV/AIDS and malaria must be stopped
	<i>k21 For sustainable development, people need to be educated in how to protect themselves against natural disasters</i>
	a1 I think that everyone ought to be given the opportunity to acquire the knowledge, values and skills that are necessary to live sustainably
	a2 I think that we who are living now should make sure that people in the future enjoy the same quality of life as we do today
	a3 I think that companies have a responsibility to reduce the use of packaging and disposable articles
	<i>a5* I think that using more natural resources than we need does not threaten the health and well-being of people in the future</i>
	<i>a6 I think that we need stricter laws and regulations to protect the environment</i>
	a7 I think it is important to reduce poverty
	a8 I think that companies in rich countries should give employees in poor nations the same conditions as in rich countries
	<i>a10 I think that it is important to take measures against problems which have to do with climate change</i>
	a11 I think that the government should provide financial aid to encourage more people to make the shift to green cars
	a13 I think that the government should make all its decisions on the basis of sustainable development
	a14 I think that it is important that people in society exercise their democratic rights and become involved in important issues

Measure	Item
a16	I think that people who pollute land, air or water should pay for the damage they cause to the environment
a18	I think that women and men throughout the world must be given the same opportunities for education and employment
a19*	<i>I think it is OK that each one of us uses as much water as we want</i>
SCQ behavior	b1
	<i>Where possible, I choose to cycle or walk when I'm going somewhere, instead of travelling by motor vehicle</i>
	b2
	<i>I never waste water</i>
	b3
	<i>I recycle as much as I can</i>
	b4
	When I use a computer or mobile to chat, to text, to play games and so on, I always treat others as respectfully as I would in real life
	b5*
	I often make lifestyle choices which are not good for my health
	b6
	I do things which help poor people
	b7
	<i>I pick up rubbish when I see it out in the countryside or in public places</i>
	b8*
	<i>I don't think about how my actions may damage the natural environment</i>
	b9
	I often purchase second-hand goods over the internet or in a shop
	b10
	<i>I always separate food waste before putting out the rubbish when I have the chance</i>
	b11
	I avoid buying goods from companies with a bad reputation for looking after their employees and the environment
	b12
	<i>I have changed my personal lifestyle in order to reduce waste (e.g., throwing away less food or not wasting materials)</i>
	b13
	I work on committees (e.g., the student council, my class committee, the cafeteria committee) at my school

Measure	Item
b14	I treat everyone with the same respect, even if they have another cultural background than mine
b15	I support an aid organization or environmental group
b16	I watch news programs or read newspaper articles to do with the economy
b17	I show the same respect to men and women, boys and girls

Note. Italicized items constitute the environmental sustainability consciousness scale.

* Reverse-coded items.

Missing Data

We aimed to test whether our primary findings remained stable when using multiple imputation in Blimp 3.2.12 (Keller & Enders, 2024) to account for missing data in our random intercept models (Hayes, 2019). Specifically, we specified a fully conditional specification (FCS) multilevel multiple imputation model for each measure of environmental attitudes separately with age and each item of the pertaining environmental attitudes measure as predictors. However, even basic models including only environmental attitudes and age failed to converge, as indicated by a highest potential scale reduction factor > 1.05 (20,000 burn-in iterations, 10,000 iterations across 2 Markov chain Monte Carlo [MCMC] chains).

Table S2*Descriptives per Included Dataset*

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M, SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M, SD</i>
NEP	2		USA	74	17.5	50.0	NEP	3.37, 0.83
NEP	7		Belgium	187	16 – 25 (22.01, 1.80)	56.1	NEP	3.65, 0.48
NEP	8	2022	USA, UK, South Africa	411	18-25 (21.96, 2.08)	68.4	NEP	3.62, 0.53
NEP	9		Belgium	148	18-25 (22.12, 2.07)	76.4	NEP	3.68, 0.49
NEP	10	2011	China	1,120	16-25 (20.20, 1.32)	47.3	NEP	3.97, 0.44
NEP	11	2013	Turkey	472	14-20 (15.75, 1.13)	40.7	NEP	3.25, 0.35
NEP	12	2016-2017	Belgium	103	18-22 (19.46, 0.74)	49.5	NEP	3.26, 0.24
NEP	15		Spain	65	18-24 (19.08, 1.34)	55.4	NEP	3.79, 0.34
NEP	17	2010	China	487	10-12	43.5	NEP	3.88, 0.52

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>
					(10.86, 0.72)			
NEP	18		China	291	18-25	57.7	NEP	4.02, 0.44
					(20.88, 1.62)			
NEP	19		USA	140	16-19	51.4	NEP	3.37, 0.48
					(17.19, 0.63)			
NEP	20		Romania	424	18-25	43.9	NEP	3.5, 0.46
					(19.61, 1.34)			
NEP	23	2012	USA	1,465	17.5-20.5	53.3	NEP	3.53, 0.56
					(18.63, 1.39)			
NEP	24		USA	42	18-23	64.3	NEP	3.62, 0.50
					(18.93, 1.40)			
NEP	25		USA	55	18-25	81.8	NEP	3.67, 0.67
					(19.55, 1.41)			
NEP	26		USA	55	18-25	85.5	NEP	3.61, 0.43
					(19.69, 1.60)			
NEP	27		USA	59	18-25	57.6	NEP	3.55, 0.57
					(19.74, 1.79)			
NEP	28		USA	280	18-25	52.1	NEP	3.19, 0.46

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>
					(20.93, 1.39)			
NEP	29		USA	263	17-25 (20.35, 1.17)	63.1	NEP	3.17, 0.45
NEP	30	2008		240	14-25 (20.59, 1.33)	45.4	NEP	3.03, 0.41
NEP	31		USA	201	17-24 (18.80, 0.99)	65.1	NEP	3.58, 0.55
NEP	32		USA	183	18-25 (19.21, 1.23)	42.6	NEP	3.45, 0.33
NEP	33		Poland	256	17-25 (21.59, 1.74)	52.7	NEP	3.48, 0.39
NEP	42		India	374	14-19 (16.04, 1.07)	52.7	NEP	3.20, 0.39
NEP	43	2019	Belgium	498	15-19 (17.1, 0.83)	41.0	NEP	3.53, 0.48
NEP	44	2021	Germany	94	14-18 (15.62, 0.86)	46.2	NEP	3.31, 0.25

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>
NEP	48	2017-2019	Galápagos Islands	33	15-18 (16.54, 0.65)	54.6	NEP	3.42, 0.59
NEP	55		Switzerland	407	18-25 (22.54, 1.9)	38.1	NEP	3.61, 0.56
NEP	58	2020	Italy	113	19-25 (23.28, 1.24)	59.3	NEP	3.4, 0.26
NEP	59		Belgium	112	18-19 (18.34, 0.48)	45.5	NEP	3.58, 0.45
NEP	60		USA	67	16-25 (22.27, 1.96)	47.8	NEP	3.17, 0.44
NEP	61		USA	65	28-25 (22.51, 1.92)	41.5	NEP	3.19, 0.48
NEP	62	2020	Germany	119	28-25 (21.46, 2.05)	44.5	NEP	2.34, 0.48
NEP	67	2019	Poland	816	17-25 (20.99, 1.78)	55.9	NEP	3.51, 0.42
NEP	68	2019	Poland	90	17-25 (20.29, 1.97)	35.6	NEP	2.53, 0.42

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M, SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M, SD</i>
NEP	69	2019	Mexico	249	17-24 (19.1, 1.33)	29.7	NEP	3.75, 0.37
NEP	70	2019	Mexico	268	17-25 (18.88, 1.24)	32.5	NEP	2.28, 0.38
NEP	71	2022	Poland	157	19-25 (21.08, 1.32)	42.3	NEP	3.5, 0.42
NEP	72	2020	Poland	336	17-25 (20.88, 1.65)	36.6	NEP	3.54, 0.43
NEP	73	2021	Poland	287	17-25 (20.95, 1.62)	44.3	NEP	3.56, 0.42
NEP/2-MEV	13	2003-2007	USA	4,484	8-13 (10.19, 0.86)	50.3	NEP	3.59, 0.49
							Preservation	3.72, 0.82
							Utilization	2.45, 0.87
NEP/2-MEV	14		USA	2,406	8-12 (9.80, 0.78)	40.1	NEP	3.59, 0.47
							Preservation	3.84, 0.78

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>
							Utilization	2.38, 0.85
NEP/2-MEV	34	2005		877	9-19 (12.67, 2.09)	58.4	NEP	3.84, 0.59
							Preservation	3.94, 0.80
							Utilization	2.59, 0.75
2-MEV	3	2018	Germany	286	19-22 (20.20, 1.47)	71.0	Preservation	3.56, 0.60
							Utilization	1.69, 0.56
2-MEV	4	2016	Nepal	199	12-19 (14.77, 1.36)	58.3	Preservation	3.84, 0.74
							Utilization	4.02, 0.63
2-MEV	5	2012-2013	Czech Republic	143	10-13 (11.38, 0.69)	51.0	Preservation	2.76, 0.53
							Utilization	4.19, 0.89
2-MEV	6 ^a	2017	USA	28	10-12 (10.5, 0.58)	53.6	Preservation	3.98, 0.41
							Utilization	2.10, 0.55
2-MEV	16		New Zealand	21	12-13	57.1	Preservation	4.06, 0.37

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>
					(12.24, 0.44)			
							Utilization	2.40, 0.55
2-MEV	21	2020	New Zealand	132	11-13 (12.24, 0.71)	46.2	Preservation	2.01, 0.67
							Utilization	3.68, 0.60
2-MEV	22		Slovenia	480	10-15 (12.16, 1.48)	51.0	Preservation	3.90, 0.54
							Utilization	2.52, 0.47
2-MEV	35	2018		84	10-12 (11.14, 0.49)	42.9	Preservation	3.96, 0.63
							Utilization	1.75, 0.62
2-MEV	36	2011	Germany	543	10-18 (13.35, 2.01)	51.9	Preservation	3.65, 0.65
							Utilization	2.25, 0.52
2-MEV	37	2011	Belgium	631	16-23 (17.59, 0.95)	27.6	Preservation	3.44, 0.74
							Utilization	2.51, 0.65

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>
2-MEV	38	2018		593	9-13 (10.50, 0.67)	48.7	Preservation	4.04, 0.58
							Utilization	2.83, 0.79
2-MEV	39	2019	Belgium	1,863	8-15 (11.34, 1.26)	46.1	Preservation	3.96, 0.60
							Utilization	2.72, 0.74
2-MEV	40	2024	USA	49	10-18 (12.86, 3.12)	24.5	Preservation	3.40, 0.48
							Utilization	4.06, 0.55
2-MEV	41			150	17-25 (20.68, 1.8)	56.0	Preservation	3.67, 0.64
							Utilization	3.36, 0.84
2-MEV	49	2021	Japan	180	15.5-15.5 (15.5, 0)	60.0	Preservation	3.59, 0.68
							Utilization	2.82, 0.72
2-MEV	50		Tanzania	407	15-24 (18.17, 1.31)	37.4	Preservation	3.92, 0.71
							Utilization	2.98, 0.62

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>
2-MEV	51	2021-2022	Germany	357	10-17 (11.74, 1.34)	56.3	Preservation	3.53, 0.76
							Utilization	2.36, 0.64
2-MEV	52		Germany	157	14-15 (14.42, 0.50)	48.4	Preservation	3.02, 0.64
							Utilization	2.39, 0.63
2-MEV	54		Germany, Brazil	447	16-25 (21.27, 2.24)	61.3	Preservation	4.19, 0.65
							Utilization	1.67, 0.53
2-MEV	64	2020	Czech Republic	29,659	10-16 (13.37, 0.99)	50.4	Preservation	
							Utilization	2.53, 0.67
2-MEV	66	2017, 2018	Germany, Austria	351	10-16 (12.59, 1.59)	41.9	Preservation	3.52, 0.82
							Utilization	2.27, 0.75
SCQ	1	2013	Sweden, Taiwan	4,141	12.5-18.5 (15.37, 2.46)	51.8	Overall SC	3.86, 0.45
							Environmental SC	3.76, 0.53

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M, SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M, SD</i>
SCQ	45		Japan	15	19-25 (23.13, 2.03)	40.0	Overall SC	3.60, 0.42
							Environmental SC	3.65, 0.50
SCQ	46		Japan	27	18-25 (22.26, 2.40)	55.6	Overall SC	3.79, 0.31
							Environmental SC	3.81, 0.41
SCQ	47		Japan	26	19-25 (22.58, 1.90)	57.7	Overall SC	3.74, 0.35
							Environmental SC	3.84, 0.46
SCQ	53	2021	Denmark	388	18-25 (21.13, 1.52)	40.0	Overall SC	4.08, 0.6
							Environmental SC	3.90, 0.75
SCQ	56	2015-2017	Greece	41	20-23 (20.76, 0.58)	75.6	Overall SC	3.81, 0.32
							Environmental SC	3.72, 0.39
SCQ	57	2019-2020	Belgium	975	8-15 (11.34, 1.26)	45.9	Overall SC	4.12, 0.47
							Environmental SC	4.00, 0.49

Measure	Dataset	Data collection			Sample		Environmental Attitudes	
		Year	Country	<i>N</i>	Age range (<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>)	Female %	Scale	<i>M</i> , <i>SD</i>
SCQ	63	2021	Spain	11	17-25 (21.72, 2.72)	72.7	Overall SC	1.63, 0.17
							Environmental SC	1.87, 0.31

Table S3*Study Reports per Included Dataset*

Dataset	Study report(s)
1	<p data-bbox="315 389 2013 469">Berglund, T., & Gericke, N. (2016). Separated and integrated perspectives on environmental, economic, and social dimensions—an investigation of student views on sustainable development. <i>Environmental Education Research</i>, 22(8), 1115-1138. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2015.1063589</p> <p data-bbox="315 496 2013 576">Berglund, T., & Gericke, N. (2018). Exploring the role of the economy in young adults' understanding of sustainable development. <i>Sustainability</i>, 10(8), 2738. https://doi.org/10.3390/su10082738</p> <p data-bbox="315 608 2013 687">Berglund, T., Gericke, N., Boeve-de Pauw, J., Olsson, D., & Chang, T. C. (2020). A cross-cultural comparative study of sustainability consciousness between students in Taiwan and Sweden. <i>Environment, Development and Sustainability</i>, 22, 6287-6313. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-019-00478-2</p> <p data-bbox="315 719 2013 799">Berglund, T., Gericke, N., & Chang Rundgren, S. N. (2014). The implementation of education for sustainable development in Sweden: Investigating the sustainability consciousness among upper secondary students. <i>Research in Science & Technological Education</i>, 32(3), 318-339. https://doi.org/10.1080/02635143.2014.944493</p> <p data-bbox="315 831 2013 911">Boeve-de-Pauw, J., Gericke, N., Olsson, D., & Berglund, T. (2015). The effectiveness of education for sustainable development. <i>Sustainability</i>, 7(11), 15693-15717. https://doi.org/10.3390/su71115693</p> <p data-bbox="315 943 2013 1023">Gericke, N., Boeve-de Pauw, J., Berglund, T., & Olsson, D. (2019). The Sustainability Consciousness Questionnaire: The theoretical development and empirical validation of an evaluation instrument for stakeholders working with sustainable development. <i>Sustainable Development</i>, 27(1), 35-49. https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1859</p> <p data-bbox="315 1054 2013 1134">Olsson, D., & Gericke, N. (2016). The adolescent dip in students' sustainability consciousness—Implications for education for sustainable development. <i>The Journal of Environmental Education</i>, 47(1), 35-51. https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2015.1075464</p> <p data-bbox="315 1166 2013 1246">Olsson, D., Gericke, N., Boeve-de Pauw, J., Berglund, T., & Chang, T. (2019). Green schools in Taiwan—Effects on student sustainability consciousness. <i>Global Environmental Change</i>, 54, 184-194. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.11.011</p> <p data-bbox="315 1278 2013 1350">Olsson, D., Gericke, N., & Chang Rundgren, S. N. (2016). The effect of implementation of education for sustainable development in Swedish compulsory schools—assessing pupils' sustainability consciousness. <i>Environmental Education Research</i>, 22(2), 176-202. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2015.1005057</p>

Dataset	Study report(s)
2	Otto, S., Evans, G. W., Moon, M. J., & Kaiser, F. G. (2019). The development of children's environmental attitude and behavior. <i>Global Environmental Change</i> , 58, 101947. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2019.101947
3	Kleespies, M. W., & Dierkes, P. W. (2020). Exploring the construct of relational values: An empirical approach. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , 11, 209. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00209
4	Regmi, S., Johnson, B., & Dahal, B. M. (2019). Analysing the environmental values and attitudes of rural Nepalese children by validating the 2-MEV model. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(1), 164. https://doi.org/10.3390/su12010164
5	Johnson, B., & Činčera, J. (2015). Examining the relationship between environmental attitudes and behaviour in education programmes. <i>Social Studies</i> , 12(3), 97-111. https://doi.org/10.5817/SOC2015-3-97
6	Schneller, A. J., Harrison, L. M., Adelman, J., & Post, S. (2021). Outcomes of art-based environmental education in the Hudson River Watershed. <i>Applied Environmental Education & Communication</i> , 20(1), 19-33. https://doi.org/10.1080/1533015X.2019.1617805
7	Lange, F., Steinke, A., & Dewitte, S. (2018). The Pro-Environmental Behavior Task: A laboratory measure of actual pro-environmental behavior. <i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i> , 56, 46-54. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2018.02.007
8	Lange, F., & Dewitte, S. (2023). Validity and scope sensitivity of the work for Environmental Protection Task. <i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i> , 86, 101967. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2023.101967
9	Lange, F., & Dewitte, S. (2022). The Work for Environmental Protection Task: A consequential web-based procedure for studying pro-environmental behavior. <i>Behavior Research Methods</i> , 54(1), 133-145. https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-021-01617-2
10	Chang, G. (2015). Materialist value orientations as correlates of the new ecological paradigm among university students in China. <i>Psychological Reports</i> , 116(2), 597-612. https://doi.org/10.2466/17.07.PR0.116k17w9
11	Dervişoğlu, S., & Tankuş, M. (2015). Factors affecting young people's behavioral commitment to the protection of local gazelle species: The case of Şanlıurfa in Turkey. <i>Journal of Baltic Science Education</i> , 14(5), 616. https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/factors-affecting-young-people-s-behavioral/docview/2343749320/se-2

Dataset	Study report(s)
12	Brusselaers, J., Verbeke, W., Mettepenningen, E., & Buysse, J. (2020). Unravelling the true drivers for eco-certified wood consumption by introducing scarcity. <i>Forest Policy and Economics</i> , 111, 102026. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2019.102026
13	Johnson, B., & Manoli, C. C. (2008). Using Bogner and Wiseman's Model of Ecological Values to measure the impact of an earth education programme on children's environmental perceptions. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 14(2), 115-127. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504620801951673 Johnson, B., & Manoli, C. C. (2010). The 2-MEV scale in the United States: A measure of children's environmental attitudes based on the theory of ecological attitude. <i>The Journal of Environmental Education</i> , 42(2), 84-97. https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2010.503716
14	Johnson, B., & Činčera, J. (2015). Examining the relationship between environmental attitudes and behaviour in education programmes. <i>Social Studies</i> , 12(3), 97-111. https://doi.org/10.5817/SOC2015-3-97
15	Sevillano, V., Corraliza, J. A., & Lorenzo, E. (2017). Spanish version of the Dispositional Empathy with Nature scale / Versión española de la escala de Empatía Disposicional hacia la Naturaleza. <i>Revista de Psicología Social</i> , 32(3), 624-658. https://doi.org/10.1080/02134748.2017.1356548
16	Watkins, L., Aitken, R., & Ford, J. (2019). Measuring and enhancing children's sustainable consumption and production literacy. <i>Young Consumers</i> , 20(4), 285-298. https://doi.org/10.1108/YC-11-2018-0880
17	Wu, L. (2012). Exploring the new ecological paradigm scale for gauging children's environmental attitudes in China. <i>The Journal of Environmental Education</i> , 43(2), 107-120. https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2011.616554
18	Wu, L., & Zhu, Y. (2021). How love of nature promotes green consumer behaviors: The mediating role of biospheric values, ecological worldview, and personal norms. <i>PsyCh Journal</i> , 10(3), 402-414. https://doi.org/10.1002/pchj.430
19	Hoover, K. S. (2021). Children in nature: exploring the relationship between childhood outdoor experience and environmental stewardship. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 27(6), 894-910. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2020.1856790
20	Pavalache-Ilie, M., & Cazan, A. M. (2018). Personality correlates of pro-environmental attitudes. <i>International Journal of Environmental Health Research</i> , 28(1), 71-78. https://doi.org/10.1080/09603123.2018.1429576
21	Watkins, L. (2020). [Unpublished raw dataset].

Dataset	Study report(s)
22	Torkar, G., Fabijan, T., & Bogner, F. X. (2020). Students' care for dogs, environmental attitudes, and behaviour. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(4), 1317. https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041317
23	Rideout, B. E. (2014). The liberal arts and environmental awareness: Exploring endorsement of an environmental worldview in college students. <i>International Journal of Environmental and Science Education</i> , 9(1), 59-76. https://doi.org/10.12973/ijese.2014.203a
24	Carlson, J. M., Lehman, B. R., & Thompson, J. L. (2019). Climate change images produce an attentional bias associated with pro-environmental disposition. <i>Cognitive Processing</i> , 20, 385-390. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10339-019-00902-5
25	Carlson, J. M., Kaull, H., Steinhauer, M., Zigarac, A., & Cammarata, J. (2020). Paying attention to climate change: Positive images of climate change solutions capture attention. <i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i> , 71, 101477. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101477
26	Carlson, J. M., Kaull, H., Steinhauer, M., Zigarac, A., & Cammarata, J. (2020). Paying attention to climate change: Positive images of climate change solutions capture attention. <i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i> , 71, 101477. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101477
27	Lehman, B., Thompson, J., Davis, S., & Carlson, J. M. (2019). Affective images of climate change. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , 10, 960. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00960
28	Wergin, R. E. (2009). <i>The frugal and the environmentally concerned: who are they, what do they do, and how do you influence them?</i> . Oklahoma State University.
29	Wergin, R. E. (2009). <i>The frugal and the environmentally concerned: who are they, what do they do, and how do you influence them?</i> . Oklahoma State University.
30	Wergin, R. E. (2008). [Unpublished raw dataset].
31	McConnell, A. R., & Jacobs, T. P. (2020). Self-nature representations: On the unique consequences of nature-self size on pro-environmental action. <i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i> , 71, 101471. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101471
32	McConnell, A. R., & Jacobs, T. P. (2020). Self-nature representations: On the unique consequences of nature-self size on pro-environmental action. <i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i> , 71, 101471. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101471
33	Caniëls, M. C., Lambrechts, W., Platje, J., Motylska-Kuźma, A., & Fortuński, B. (2021). 50 shades of green: Insights into personal values and worldviews as drivers of green purchasing intention, behaviour, and experience. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13(8), 4140. https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084140
34	Randler, C. (2005). [Unpublished raw dataset].

Dataset	Study report(s)
35	Rögele A. (2021). <i>Scientific reasoning and citizen science: Enabling students and adults to become scientifically literate citizens of tomorrow's society</i> . [Doctoral Dissertation, University of Tübingen]. https://ub01.uni-tuebingen.de/xmlui/handle/10900/116436
36	Binngießer, J., & Randler, C. (2015). Association of the environmental attitudes "preservation" and "utilization" with pro-animal attitudes. <i>International Journal of Environmental and Science Education</i> , 10(3), 477-492.
37	Boeve-de Pauw, J., & Van Petegem, P. (2017). Because my friends insist or because it makes sense? Adolescents' motivation towards the environment. <i>Sustainability</i> , 9(5), 750. https://doi.org/10.3390/su9050750
38	Boeve-de Pauw, J. (2018). [Unpublished raw dataset].
39	Sass, W., Pauw, J. B. D., Maeyer, S. D., & Petegem, P. V. (2021). Development and validation of an instrument for measuring action competence in sustainable development within early adolescents: The Action Competence in Sustainable Development Questionnaire (ACiSD-Q). <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 27(9), 1284-1304. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2021.1888887
40	Schneller, A. J. (2024). [Unpublished raw dataset].
41	Nkaizirwa, J. P., Aurah, C. M., & Nsanganwimana, F. (2022). An empirical investigation of environmental knowledge and attitudes as the correlates of environmental identity among pre-service biology teachers in Tanzania. <i>Sustainability</i> , 15(1), 669. https://doi.org/10.3390/su15010669 Nkaizirwa, J. P., Aurah, C. M., & Nsanganwimana, F. (2023). Data collected to assess the effect of inquiry-based learning on environmental knowledge and attitudes among pre-service biology teachers in Tanzania. <i>Data in Brief</i> , 49, 109429. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109429
42	Mathew, T., & Parameswari, J. (2023). Exploring the relationship between spirituality, environmental attitude, and positive youth development: The mediating role of environmental commitment and psychological well-being. <i>Trends in Psychology</i> , 1-20. https://doi.org/10.1007/s43076-023-00350-3
43	Waeterloos, C., Conradie, P., Walrave, M., & Ponnet, K. (2021). Digital issue movements: Political repertoires and drivers of participation among Belgian youth in the context of 'school strike for climate'. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13(17), 9892. https://doi.org/10.3390/su13179892

Dataset	Study report(s)
44	Bengel, P. T., & Peter, C. (2022). Technology in nature—mDGBL as a successful approach to promote complex contents?. <i>Sustainability</i> , 15(1), 633. https://doi.org/10.3390/su15010633
45	Ogishima, H., Ito, A., Kajimura, S., & Himichi, T. (2023). Validity and reliability of the Japanese version of the sustainability consciousness questionnaire. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , 14, 1130550. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1130550
46	Ogishima, H., Ito, A., Kajimura, S., & Himichi, T. (2023). Validity and reliability of the Japanese version of the sustainability consciousness questionnaire. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , 14, 1130550. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1130550
47	Ogishima, H., Ito, A., Kajimura, S., & Himichi, T. (2023). Validity and reliability of the Japanese version of the sustainability consciousness questionnaire. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , 14, 1130550. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1130550
48	Weisberg, D. S., Kovaka, K., Vaca, E., & Weisberg, M. (2023). LAVA-Lobos: Raising environmental awareness through community science in the Galápagos Islands. <i>Citizen Science: Theory and Practice</i> , 8(1). https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.423
49	Kurokawa, H., Igei, K., Kitsuki, A., Kurita, K., Managi, S., Nakamuro, M., & Sakano, A. (2023). Improvement impact of nudges incorporated in environmental education on students' environmental knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 325, 116612. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116612
50	Nkaizirwa, J. P., Nsanganwimana, F., & Aurah, C. M. (2022). On the predictors of pro-environmental behaviors: integrating personal values and the 2-MEV among secondary school students in Tanzania. <i>Heliyon</i> , 8(3), e09064.
51	Schmäing, T., & Grotjohann, N. (2022). Out-of-School learning in the Wadden Sea: The influence of a mudflat hiking tour on the environmental attitudes and environmental knowledge of secondary school students. <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i> , 20(1), 403. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20010403
52	Schmäing, T., & Grotjohann, N. (2023). Environmental education in teaching science on the Wadden Sea ecosystem: What are the effects on environmental psychological constructs?. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 29(2), 232-247. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2102584
53	Jebsen, S., Senderovitz, M., & Winkler, I. (2023). Shades of green: A latent profile analysis of sustainable entrepreneurial attitudes among business students. <i>The International Journal of Management Education</i> , 21(3), 100860. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100860

Dataset	Study report(s)
54	de Almeida Barbosa, R., Randler, C., & Robaina, J. V. L. (2021). Values and environmental knowledge of student participants of climate strikes: a comparative perspective between Brazil and Germany. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13(14), 8010. https://doi.org/10.3390/su13148010
55	Berger, S., & Wyss, A. M. (2021). Measuring pro-environmental behavior using the carbon emission task. <i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i> , 75, 101613. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2021.101613
56	Malandrakis, G. (2022). The contribution of sustainability education pedagogies to the development of Greek preservice teachers' sustainability consciousness about social issues in urban environments. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 28(3), 382-404. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2021.1969338
57	Verachtert, S. (2023). Family congruence in sustainability attitudes and behaviour; an analysis of a household survey in Belgium. <i>Environment, Development and Sustainability</i> , 25(11), 12467-12493. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02575-1 Verachtert, S., & Stiers, D. (2024). The heterogeneous effects of an education for sustainable development intervention in schools: Evidence from a Belgian panel study. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 30(3), 462-478. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2128062
58	Scopelliti, M., Barni, D., & Rinallo, E. (2022). My parents taught... green was my growth! The role of intergenerational transmission of ecological values in young adults' pro-environmental behaviors and their psychosocial mechanisms. <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i> , 19(3), 1670. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19031670
59	Goethals, F., & Ziegelmayer, J. L. (2024). The greening of IT use: The impact of environmental concerns on the use of internet systems. <i>Information Technology & People</i> , 37(1), 356-373. https://doi-org.utrechtuniversity.idm.oclc.org/10.1108/ITP-11-2021-0844
60	Goethals, F., & Ziegelmayer, J. L. (2024). The greening of IT use: The impact of environmental concerns on the use of internet systems. <i>Information Technology & People</i> , 37(1), 356-373. https://doi-org.utrechtuniversity.idm.oclc.org/10.1108/ITP-11-2021-0844
61	Goethals, F., & Ziegelmayer, J. L. (2024). The greening of IT use: The impact of environmental concerns on the use of internet systems. <i>Information Technology & People</i> , 37(1), 356-373. https://doi-org.utrechtuniversity.idm.oclc.org/10.1108/ITP-11-2021-0844

Dataset	Study report(s)
62	Bastini, K., Kerschreiter, R., Lachmann, M., Ziegler, M., & Sawert, T. (2024). Encouraging individual contributions to net-zero organizations: Effects of behavioral policy interventions and social norms. <i>Journal of Business Ethics</i> , 192(3), 543-560. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-023-05516-8
63	Ariza, M. R., Boeve-de Pauw, J., Olsson, D., Van Petegem, P., Parra, G., & Gericke, N. (2021). Promoting environmental citizenship in education: The potential of the sustainability consciousness questionnaire to measure impact of interventions. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13(20), 11420. https://doi.org/10.3390/su132011420
64	Cincera, J., Kroufek, R., & Bogner, F. X. (2023). The perceived effect of environmental and sustainability education on environmental literacy of Czech teenagers. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 29(9), 1276-1293. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2107618
65	Berger, S., & Wyss, A. M. (2021). Measuring pro-environmental behavior using the carbon emission task. <i>Journal of Environmental Psychology</i> , 75, 101613. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2021.101613
66	Neurohr, A. L., Pasch, N., Otto, S., & Möller, A. (2023). Measuring adolescents' level of interest in nature: a promising psychological factor facilitating nature protection. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i> , 14, 1186557. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1186557
67	Platje, J., Motylska-Kuzma, A., Caniels, M., & Will, M. (2023). The New Ecological Paradigm, functional stupidity and university sustainability – A Polish case study. In: Nguyen, N.T., Kowalczyk, R., Mercik, J., Motylska-Kuźma, A. (eds) <i>Transactions on Computational Collective Intelligence XXXVII</i> (pp. 117-135). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-66597-8_7
68	Platje, J. (2019). [Unpublished raw dataset].
69	Quintana, D. S. Z., Platje, J., Bernaciak, A., Czekala, M., Will, M., & van Dam, Y. K. (2024). The new ecological paradigm and attitudes towards sustainable business practices – a Mexican case study. <i>Economics and Environment</i> , 87(4), 1-21. https://doi.org/10.34659/eis.2023.87.4.649
70	Platje, J. (2019). [Unpublished raw dataset].
71	Platje, J. (2022). [Unpublished raw dataset].
72	Platje, J. (2020). [Unpublished raw dataset].

Dataset	Study report(s)
73	Platje, J., Will, M., Paradowska, M., & van Dam, Y. K. (2022). Socioeconomic paradigms and the perception of system risks: A study of attitudes towards nuclear power among Polish business students. <i>Energies</i> , 15(19), 7313. https://doi.org/10.3390/en15197313

Results

Primary Analyses

Historical Time Trends in Environmental Attitudes

We specified—for each environmental attitudes scale separately—a series of random-intercept multilevel models with environmental attitudes regressed on year of data collection, controlling for age. Here, we report the details of these analyses.

NEP. For the NEP, the quadratic model fitted our data best (Table S4). The quadratic model ($R^2 = 24.4\%$, intercept NEP scores = 3.60, $SE = 0.10$) showed that year of data collection did not significantly predict endorsement of the new ecological paradigm (linear effect: $b = -0.01$, $SE = 0.10$, $\beta = -.08$, $p = .577$; quadratic effect: $b < -0.18$, $SE < 0.01$, $\beta = .03$, $p = .111$; Figure S1, panel A).

2-MEV. For the 2-MEV preservation subscale, where higher scores reflect more favorable environmental attitudes, the linear model fitted our data best (Table S4). The linear model ($R^2 = 12.7\%$, intercept preservation scores = 3.74, $SE = 0.15$) again showed that year of data collection did not significantly predict endorsement of nature preservation (linear effect: $b < 0.01$, $SE = 0.03$, $\beta < 0.01$, $p = .980$; Figure S1, panel B).

Similarly, for the 2-MEV utilization subscale, where higher scores reflect less favorable environmental attitudes, the linear model fitted our data best (Table S4). The linear model ($R^2 = 9.1\%$, intercept utilization scores = 2.69, $SE = 0.15$) again showed that year of data collection did not significantly predict endorsement of nature utilization ($b = 0.02$, $SE = 0.03$, $\beta = 0.13$, $p = .520$; Figure S1, panel C).

SCQ. For the overall SCQ scale, where higher scores reflect more sustainability consciousness, the linear model fitted our data best (Table S4). The linear model ($R^2 = 10.5\%$, intercept sustainability consciousness scores = 3.86, $SE = 0.46$) again showed that year of data

collection did not significantly predict knowingness, attitudes, and behaviors concerning environmental, social, and economic sustainability (linear effect: $b = -0.06$, $SE = 0.10$, $\beta = -0.35$, $p = .588$; Figure S1, panel D). Similarly, for the environmental SCQ scale, where higher scores reflect more environmental sustainability consciousness, the linear model fitted our data best (Table S4). The linear model ($R^2 = 6.2\%$, intercept environmental sustainability consciousness scores = 3.72, $SE = 0.40$) again showed that year of data collection did not significantly predict knowingness, attitudes, and behaviors concerning environmental sustainability (linear effect: $b = -0.05$, $SE = 0.08$, $\beta = -0.27$, $p = .590$; Figure S1, panel D).

Summary. Together, we found no evidence for historical time trends in adolescents' environmental attitudes.

Table S4*Model Comparisons for Historical Time Trends in Environmental Attitudes, Controlling for Age*

Model	AIC	BIC	Log likelihood	Deviance
NEP ($N = 18,939$)				
Null	26046	26069	-13020	26040
Linear	26040	26079	-13015	26030
Quadratic	26039	26086	-13014	26027
General additive model	29101	29203	-14538	5148
2-MEV preservation ($N = 14,848$)				
Null	33088	33111	-16541	33082
Linear	32911	32949	-16450	32901
Quadratic	32913	32958	-16450	32901
General additive model	34018	34117	-16996	8579
2-MEV utilization ($N = 44,519$)				
Null	95257	95283	-47625	95251
Linear	95242	95286	-47616	95232
Quadratic	95243	95295	-47616	95231
General additive model	97516	97629	-48745	23287
SCQ overall ($N = 6,507$)				
Null	8481	8502	-4238	8475

Linear	8459	8493	-4225	8449
Quadratic	8461	8501	-4224	8449
General additive model ^a	8719	8746	-4355	1453
SCQ environmental ($N = 6,504$)				
Null	10300	10321	-5147	10294
Linear	10299	10333	-5145	10289
Quadratic	10301	10341	-5144	10289
General additive model ^a	10410	10450	-5199	1884

Note. Bolded values indicate the best fit. The sample size difference between the 2-MEV preservation and utilization scales is mostly caused by one large dataset that we did obtain utilization but not preservation scores for.

^a The default number of knots ($k = 10$) was reduced to the maximum number of knots given the number of unique values for year of data collection in these samples ($k = 4$).

Figure S1

Modeled Historical Time Trends in Environmental Attitudes, Controlling for Age

Note. For green (versus red) trends, higher values reflect more (versus less) favorable environmental attitudes. Panel A models quadratic time differences in NEP scores. Panel B and C model linear time differences in 2-MEV preservation and utilization scores, respectively. Panel D and E model linear time differences in overall and environmental SCQ scores, respectively.

Exploratory Analyses

We examined measurement invariance for each environmental attitude scale. That is, we examined whether the scales were psychometrically equivalent across three age groups: children or early adolescents (ages 8-12), middle adolescents (ages 13-17), and late adolescents or emerging adults (ages 18-25). When measurement invariance is established for a scale, this demonstrates that the scale is interpreted in the same way across age groups. Measurement invariance typically involves three steps of increasingly restrictive confirmatory factor analysis models, establishing (a) configural invariance (i.e. good model fit across age groups, without constraints), (b) metric invariance (i.e. similarly good model fit, while constraining item loadings across age groups), and (c) scalar invariance (i.e. similarly good model fit, while constraining item loadings and intercepts across age groups).

We chose to specify one-factor models for all environmental attitude scales to ensure alignment with our primary analyses that were based on single scale scores. As the results of our measurement invariance analyses show (Table S5), the NEP and environmental SCQ scales showed poor fit for configural invariance. We were unable to test measurement invariance for the overall SCQ scale because the models did not converge. The 2-MEV utilization scale showed acceptable fit for configural but not metric invariance, and the 2-MEV preservation scale showed acceptable fit for configural and metric but not scalar invariance. Importantly, these findings may be at least in part attributable to missingness and differences in scale adaptations between datasets. Still, they indicate that young people of different ages experience and interpret the scale items differently, which is important to consider when examining age trends in environmental attitudes.

Table S5*Measurement Invariance Analysis for Each Environmental Attitude Scale Separately*

NEP												
Model	X ²	df X ²	ΔX ²	CFI	ΔCFI	TLI	RMSEA	95% CI RMSEA	P-Close	ΔRMSEA	SRMR	Interpretation
Configural	12,285	270		0.721		0.675	0.084	[0.083; 0.085]	<.001		0.085	Poor fit
Metric	12,751	298	466***	0.711	-0.010	0.695	0.081	[0.080; 0.083]	<.001	-0.003	0.091	Reject
Scalar												-
2-MEV preservation												
Model	X ²	df X ²	ΔX ²	CFI	ΔCFI	TLI	RMSEA	95% CI RMSEA	P-Close	ΔRMSEA	SRMR	Interpretation
Configural	1,163	105		0.902		0.874	0.045	[0.043; 0.048]	1.000		0.043	Acceptable fit
Metric	1,253	123	90	0.895	-0.007	0.885	0.043	[0.041; 0.045]	1.000	-0.002	0.051	Accept
Scalar	1,649	141	396***	0.860	-0.035	0.866	0.047	[0.045; 0.049]	0.998	0.004	0.062	Reject
2-MEV utilization												
Model	X ²	df X ²	ΔX ²	CFI	ΔCFI	TLI	RMSEA	95% CI RMSEA	P-Close	ΔRMSEA	SRMR	Interpretation
Configural	1,161	105		0.937		0.919	0.026	[0.025; 0.027]	1.000		0.061	Acceptable fit
Metric	1,771	123	610***	0.901	-0.036	0.891	0.030	[0.029; 0.031]	1.000	0.004	0.079	Reject
Scalar												-
SCQ environmental ^a												
Model	X ²	df X ²	ΔX ²	CFI	ΔCFI	TLI	RMSEA	95% CI RMSEA	P-Close	ΔRMSEA	SRMR	Interpretation
Configural	5,661	238		0.665		0.617	0.084	[0.082; 0.086]	<.001		0.089	Poor fit
Metric	6,090	254	429***	0.639	-0.026	0.614	0.084	[0.082; 0.086]	<.001	0.000	0.098	Reject
Scalar												-

Note. All models were run with full information maximum likelihood estimation. Fit was considered acceptable for CFI and TLI values $>.90$ (good fit if $>.95$), for RMSEA and SRMR $<.08$ (good fit if $<.05$) (Byrne, 2001; Hu & Bentler, 1999). To compare measurement models, we conducted difference tests (denoted by Δ) in the X^2 , in the CFI, and in the RMSEA between models. We accepted more restricted models over simpler models when two of the following criteria were met: $\Delta X^2 p >.05$, $\Delta CFI <.01$, and $\Delta RMSEA <.015$ (Chen, 2007).

*** $p < .001$

^a Here, we compared two (instead of three) age groups: early and middle adolescents (ages 8-18) and late adolescents or emerging adults (ages 19-25). This was necessary because the model with three age groups failed to converge.

Table S6*Sensitivity Analyses for Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes: Including Preregistered Covariates*

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
NEP (<i>N</i> = 17,112)					
Intercept	3.61	0.12	35.37	29.73	< .001
Linear age	0.02	0.02	16,421.73	0.90	.37
Quadratic age	-0.01	0.01	17,071.44	-1.11	.27
Female vs male	-0.09	0.01	17,073.34	-12.93	< .001
Female vs other	0.01	0.11	17,068.44	0.12	.90
Female vs rather not say	0.01	0.18	17,067.89	0.03	.97
Scale reliability	0.05	0.05	36.32	1.05	.30
Scale missingness	-0.03	0.28	36.11	-0.11	.91
Study sample size	0.14	0.24	35.87	0.56	.58
Cross-sectional vs longitudinal design	-0.21	0.38	36.77	-0.55	.59
Cross-sectional vs (quasi-)experimental design	-0.14	0.12	36.02	-1.14	.26
2-MEV preservation (<i>N</i> = 13,098)					
Intercept	3.81	0.22	13.59	17.50	< .001
Linear age	-0.26	0.02	12,583.06	-12.96	< .001
Quadratic age	0.13	0.01	12,895.63	8.78	< .001
Female vs male	-0.09	0.01	13,078.01	-7.41	< .001

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Female vs other	0.09	0.30	13,077.14	0.29	.77
Female vs rather not say	0.25	0.28	13,078.11	0.90	.37
Scale reliability	0.13	0.08	13.89	1.51	.15
Scale missingness	0.09	0.11	13.93	0.85	.41
Study sample size	-0.02	0.22	13.70	-0.11	.91
Cross-sectional vs (quasi-)experimental design	-0.16	0.33	13.78	-0.47	.64
2-MEV utilization (<i>N</i> = 42,735)					
Intercept	2.55	0.49	14.81	5.21	< .001
Linear age	0.03	0.01	41,958.64	4.17	< .001
Quadratic age	0.01	0.01	41,144.22	1.66	.10
Girl vs boy	-0.04	0.01	42,711.09	-6.00	< .001
Girl vs other	-0.05	0.29	42,715.26	-0.17	.86
Girl vs rather not say	-0.19	0.27	42,716.46	-0.71	.48
Scale reliability	-0.09	0.20	14.88	-0.46	.65
Scale missingness	0.15	0.13	15.95	1.13	.27
Study sample size	-0.29	0.38	14.84	-0.78	.45
Cross-sectional vs (quasi-)experimental design	0.03	0.42	14.95	0.08	.94
SCQ overall (<i>N</i> = 6,456)					
Intercept	3.95	0.06	0.11	68.71	.52
Linear age	-0.08	0.01	6,444.00	-8.40	< .001

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Quadratic age	0.09	0.01	6,391.13	9.26	< .001
Female vs male	-0.14	0.01	6,444.58	-12.58	< .001
Female vs rather not say	0.97	0.45	6,444.10	2.14	.03
Scale reliability	-0.07	0.05	0.57	-1.43	.49
Scale missingness	0.11	0.05	0.45	2.07	.46
Study sample size	0.17	0.04	0.34	4.06	.42
Cross-sectional vs longitudinal design	0.23	0.13	0.25	1.85	.62
Cross-sectional vs (quasi-)experimental design	-2.84	0.23	0.46	-12.18	.21
Cross-sectional vs mixed methods	0.28	0.12	0.47	2.25	.43
SCQ environmental (<i>N</i> = 6,453)					
Intercept	3.85	0.08	0.19	48.44	.36
Linear age	-0.01	0.01	6,441.01	-1.27	.21
Quadratic age	0.10	0.01	6,338.12	9.18	< .001
Female vs boy	-0.14	0.01	6,441.94	-10.44	< .001
Female vs rather not say	1.25	0.53	6,441.05	2.38	.02
Scale reliability	0.07	0.09	0.88	0.84	.57
Scale missingness	0.16	0.11	0.73	1.49	.43
Study sample size	0.11	0.04	0.36	2.61	.47
Cross-sectional vs longitudinal design	0.19	0.15	0.27	1.31	.66
Cross-sectional vs (quasi-)experimental design	-2.35	0.31	0.77	-7.55	.13

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Cross-sectional vs mixed methods	0.14	0.16	0.63	0.89	.60

Note. All continuous predictors were standardized to ensure similar scaling.

Table S7*Sensitivity Analyses for Historical Time Trends in Environmental Attitudes: Including Preregistered Covariates*

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
NEP (<i>N</i> = 17,112)					
Intercept	3.59	0.12	31.63	29.07	< .001
Linear time	0.09	0.11	31.80	0.75	.46
Quadratic time	-0.16	0.07	33.54	-2.29	.03
Linear age	0.01	0.01	16,352.86	0.38	.70
Female vs male	-0.09	0.01	17,072.31	-12.90	< .001
Female vs other	0.02	0.11	17,067.51	0.14	.89
Female vs rather not say	0.01	0.18	17,066.55	0.06	.96
Scale reliability	0.05	0.05	32.48	1.03	.31
Scale missingness	-0.06	0.28	32.18	-0.22	.83
Study sample size	0.13	0.26	32.09	0.50	.62
Cross-sectional vs longitudinal design	-0.36	0.39	32.89	-0.93	.36
Cross-sectional vs (quasi-)experimental design	-0.17	0.12	32.19	-1.40	.17
2-MEV preservation (<i>N</i> = 13,098)					
Intercept	3.81	0.24	12.70	15.68	< .001
Linear time	0.02	0.33	12.74	0.07	.95
Linear age	-0.18	0.02	11,764.06	-10.14	< .001

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Female vs male	-0.09	0.01	13,078.33	-7.39	< .001
Female vs other	-0.06	0.30	13,076.35	-0.19	.85
Female vs rather not say	0.10	0.28	13,076.83	0.37	.71
Scale reliability	0.14	0.10	12.89	1.37	.19
Scale missingness	0.13	0.14	12.92	0.94	.37
Study sample size	-0.00	0.32	12.81	-0.01	.99
Cross-sectional vs (quasi-)experimental design	-0.18	0.45	12.80	-0.39	0.70
2-MEV utilization (<i>N</i> = 42,735)					
Intercept	2.55	0.50	13.88	5.13	< .001
Linear time	-0.04	0.23	13.92	-0.16	.88
Linear age	0.03	0.01	41,278.54	4.59	< .001
Female vs male	-0.04	0.01	42,712.11	-5.99	< .001
Female vs other	-0.08	0.29	42,713.26	-0.26	.79
Female vs rather not say	-0.22	0.27	42,713.76	-0.81	.42
Scale reliability	-0.08	0.20	13.94	-0.42	.68
Scale missingness	0.16	0.14	13.97	1.18	.26
Study sample size	-0.29	0.39	13.91	-0.76	.46
Cross-sectional vs (quasi-)experimental design	0.08	0.51	13.98	0.15	.88

Note. All continuous predictors were standardized to ensure similar scaling. Analyses could not be performed for the SCQ scales due to convergence issues.

Table S8*Sensitivity Analyses for Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes: Downweighing Potential Influential Outliers*

Model parameters	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>	Downweighted	
				residuals (%)	clusters (<i>n</i>)
NEP (<i>N</i> = 18,939)				21.4	9
Intercept	3.48	0.04	77.60		
Linear age	0.01	0.00	3.30		
Quadratic age	-0.00	0.00	-3.00		
2-MEV preservation (<i>N</i> = 14,848)				20.5	5
Intercept	3.78	0.07	54.70		
Linear age	-0.09	0.01	-16.50		
Quadratic age	0.01	0.00	9.70		
2-MEV utilization (<i>N</i> = 44,519)				20.2	7
Intercept	2.59	0.14	18.48		
Linear age	0.01	0.00	3.89		
Quadratic age	0.00	0.00	0.81		
SCQ overall (<i>N</i> = 6,507)				20.5	0
Intercept	3.65	0.14	26.69		
Linear age	-0.02	0.00	-7.73		
Quadratic age	0.01	0.00	9.27		

Model parameters	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>	Downweighted	
				residuals (%)	clusters (<i>n</i>)
SCQ environmental (<i>N</i> = 6,504)				20.7	0
Intercept	3.46	0.13	25.95		
Linear age	-0.00	0.00	-0.52		
Quadratic age	0.01	0.00	9.43		

Note. The *robustlmm* package does not support *p* values for fixed effects.

Table S9*Sensitivity Analyses for Historical Time Trends in Environmental Attitudes: Downweighing Potential Influential Outliers*

Model parameters	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>	Downweighted	
				residuals (%)	clusters (<i>n</i>)
NEP (<i>N</i> = 18,939)				21.6	9
Intercept	3.61	0.08	47.30		
Linear time	0.00	0.01	0.10		
Quadratic time	-0.00	0.00	-1.90		
Linear age	0.01	0.00	2.10		
2-MEV preservation (<i>N</i> = 14,848)				20.8	5
Intercept	3.83	0.10	36.80		
Linear time	0.00	0.02	0.00		
Linear age	-0.07	0.00	-13.50		
2-MEV utilization (<i>N</i> = 44,519)				20.2	7
Intercept	2.62	0.14	18.28		
Linear time	0.02	0.03	0.77		
Linear age	0.01	0.00	4.15		
SCQ overall (<i>N</i> = 6,507)				21.0	0
Intercept	3.91	0.15	25.66		
Linear time	-0.01	0.03	-0.16		
Linear age	-0.01	0.00	-5.06		

Model parameters	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>	Downweighted	
				residuals (%)	clusters (<i>n</i>)
SCQ environmental (<i>N</i> = 6,504)				20.3	0
Intercept	3.77	0.13	30.10		
Linear time	-0.00	0.03	-0.17		
Linear age	0.01	0.00	2.35		

Note. The *robustlmm* package does not support *p* values for fixed effects.

Table S10*Sensitivity Analyses for Historical Time Trends in Environmental Attitudes: Substituting Proxy of -2 Years With -3 Years*

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
NEP (<i>N</i> = 18,939)					
Intercept	3.62	0.10	41.71	38.01	< .001
Linear year	-0.01	0.01	39.19	-0.52	.61
Quadratic year	-0.01	0.00	41.66	-2.08	.04
Linear age	0.01	0.00	16,617.78	2.88	.004
2-MEV preservation (<i>N</i> = 14,848)					
Intercept	3.75	0.15	20.64	24.40	< .001
Linear year	-0.00	0.03	20.70	-0.10	.92
Linear age	-0.07	0.00	12,355.38	-13.60	< .001
2-MEV utilization (<i>N</i> = 44,519)					
Intercept	2.70	0.15	21.98	17.99	< .001
Linear year	0.02	0.03	21.82	0.77	.45
Linear age	0.01	0.00	43,052.80	4.24	< .001
SCQ overall (<i>N</i> = 6,507)					
Intercept	3.90	0.44	5.76	8.77	< .001
Linear year	-0.07	0.10	5.80	-0.70	.51
Linear age	-0.01	0.00	6,503.71	-5.09	< .001

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
SCQ environmental (<i>N</i> = 6,504)					
Intercept	3.75	0.39	5.60	9.60	< .001
Linear year	-0.06	0.09	5.65	-0.71	.50
Linear age	0.01	0.00	6,493.48	2.19	.03

Table S11*Exploratory Moderation of Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes by Gender (Girls Versus Boys)*

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
NEP (<i>N</i> = 18,202)					
Intercept	3.47	0.06	46.08	61.35	<.001
Linear age	.02	0.00	14,800.34	6.98	<.001
Quadratic age	-.00	0.00	18,085.20	-4.65	<.001
Male	-.11	0.01	18,162.05	-9.36	<.001
Linear age * male	-.01	0.00	18,159.90	-8.58	<.001
Quadratic age * male	.00	0.00	18,158.39	2.43	.02
2-MEV preservation (<i>N</i> = 14,089)					
Intercept	3.72	0.11	22.30	34.59	<.001
Linear age	-.08	0.01	13,126.21	-13.20	<.001
Quadratic age	.01	0.00	13,915.02	7.09	<.001
Male	-.12	0.02	14,070.32	-7.45	<.001
Linear age * male	-.01	0.01	14,071.62	-1.00	.32
Quadratic age * male	.00	0.00	14,065.40	1.41	.16
2-MEV utilization (<i>N</i> = 43,738)					
Intercept	2.69	0.15	23.00	18.47	<.001
Linear age	.02	0.00	43,189.10	5.08	<.001

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Quadratic age	-.00	0.00	42,255.08	-1.65	.10
Male	-.06	0.01	43,709.95	-7.86	<.001
Linear age * male	-.01	0.00	43,714.33	-3.95	<.001
Quadratic age * male	.00	0.00	43,718.54	6.85	<.001
SCQ overall (<i>N</i> = 6,455)					
Intercept	3.50	0.29	6.97	11.89	<.001
Linear age	-.02	0.00	6,445.87	-4.73	<.001
Quadratic age	.01	0.00	6,448.40	6.44	<.001
Male	-.16	0.02	6,442.36	-10.65	<.001
Linear age * male	-.02	0.00	6,442.37	-4.58	<.001
Quadratic age * male	.00	0.00	6,442.68	1.93	.05
SCQ environmental (<i>N</i> = 6,452)					
Intercept	3.36	0.27	6.95	12.58	<.001
Linear age	.01	0.00	6,444.58	1.87	.06
Quadratic age	.01	0.00	6,436.97	5.82	<.001
Male	-.17	0.02	6,439.60	-9.73	<.001
Linear age * male	-.02	0.00	6,439.61	-5.57	<.001
Quadratic age * male	.00	0.00	6,440.10	2.88	.004

Figure S2*Modeled Age by Gender Interactions in Environmental Attitudes*

Note. Panel A models quadratic age differences in NEP scores. Panel B and C model quadratic age differences in 2-MEV preservation and utilization scores, respectively. Panel D and E model quadratic age differences in overall and environmental SCQ scores, respectively.

Table S12*Exploratory Moderation of Age Trends in Environmental Attitudes by Country (Global North Versus Global South)*

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
NEP (<i>N</i> = 18,939)					
Intercept	3.44	0.06	47.44	56.95	<.001
Linear age	.01	0.00	16,173.52	4.18	<.001
Quadratic age	-.00	0.00	18,838.94	-2.54	.01
Global South	-.14	0.06	2,496.23	-2.25	.02
Linear age * Global South	.01	0.01	5,021.77	0.61	.54
Quadratic age * Global South	-.00	0.00	10,112.71	-1.77	.08
2-MEV preservation (<i>N</i> = 14,764)					
Intercept	3.68	0.11	21.39	32.23	<.001
Linear age	-.09	0.01	13,426.49	-16.73	<.001
Quadratic age	.01	0.00	9,056.02	6.27	<.001
Global South	-.63	0.21	3,440.60	-3.01	.002
Linear age * Global South	.18	0.05	12,043.57	3.88	<.001
Quadratic age * Global South	-.01	0.00	14,064.10	-2.70	.01
2-MEV utilization (<i>N</i> = 44,435)					
Intercept	2.61	0.14	22.53	18.01	<.001
Linear age	.01	0.00	42,376.05	4.60	<.001

Model parameters	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Quadratic age	.00	0.00	27,868.85	4.67	<.001
Global South	.98	0.17	10,279.70	5.66	<.001
Linear age * Global South	-.12	0.04	35,931.35	-2.99	.002
Quadratic age * Global South	.00	0.00	42,501.50	0.33	.74

Note. We did not perform these analyses for the SCQ scales as these data relied exclusively on Global North countries.